

Composite adsorbents based on natural zeolite for selective removal of toxic metals and radionuclides

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The development of effective adsorbent materials for the selective removal of heavy metals and radionuclides from contaminated water and soil is a global problem, as these toxic metals can accumulate in the human body through the food chain.

Natural zeolites have long been used to bind toxic metals in soil and decontaminate radioactive water due to their efficiency and low cost. However, their wider application for selective removal of toxic metals is limited due to the decreasing selectivity with increasing solution salinity and the reversible nature of adsorption.

The synthesis of composite adsorbents based on natural zeolites with a sorption-active inorganic phase deposited on their surface seems to be a promising approach for obtaining inexpensive adsorption materials with high selectivity for specific metals/radionuclides.

Within the framework of the MSCA4Ukraine project, the synthesis of composite adsorbents based on natural zeolite was developed and implemented. The results of the synthesis of composite adsorbents for the selective removal of cesium radionuclides and heavy metals (Pb, Cd, As, etc.) based on clinoptilolite tuff from the Sokyrnytsia deposit (Ukraine) are considered. The adsorbent for cesium was synthesized by deposition of potassium-copper ferrocyanide phase on the surface of zeolite tuff, while various adsorbents for heavy metals were synthesized by deposition of FeOOH and /or MnOOH phases. Samples of natural and composite clinoptilolite tuffs were tested for the selective removal of ¹³⁷Cs and heavy metals from single and multi-component model solutions, as well as from soil solutions. The presence of the inorganic phase was shown to increase the selectivity of the composite adsorbent compared to natural clinoptilolite and to improve the fixation of adsorbed ions.